

AIConstruct:

Tackling over-budget construction projects
with AI-integrated immersive technology

AIConstruct:

Tackling over-budget construction projects with AI-integrated immersive technology

Authors:

Nompumelelo Mtsweni (AIConstruct)
Stuart Gillespie (Independent Contractor)
Sofia Pires (The Alan Turing Institute)

Additional contributors

Guanhui Lee (AIConstruct)
Mark Hester (AIConstruct)
Arielle Bennett (The Alan Turing Institute)
Léllé Demertzi (The Alan Turing Institute)

Topic overview

This case study explores how startup **AIConstruct** is developing an AI-integrated immersive platform designed to help construction teams compare planned building models with on-site reality. Founded by software developer and Cesium-certified engineer Nompumelelo (Lelo) Mtsweni, the company aims to reduce cost overruns, delays, waste and corrective work in the construction sector. Participation in The Turing Way Practitioners Hub has influenced the project's development – particularly in areas such as data readiness, international standards, and version control.

Addressing a “classic problem” in construction

From the Scottish Parliament to the Channel Tunnel, major building projects run over budget and time so frequently that it can feel like an inevitability. It happens on a smaller scale, too – and for Lelo it became personal when her family's home build exceeded both its schedule and cost projections. Frustrated by the lack of transparency about where the time and money were going, she set her mind to tackling a simple-sounding problem: why do so many construction projects fail to match their original plans? The startup she co-founded, AIConstruct, uses a combination of immersive technology and AI to identify risks and delivery deviations, linking ground-truth to schemas, and, in turn, improving accountability and problem-solving capabilities in construction.

“It's known as a classic problem everywhere in the world,” says Lelo. “When I speak to people I know in Africa, North America, Europe, they always tell me it's the same story. I asked myself, ‘why do we accept this?’ That's when I started thinking about how we could use technology to identify mismatches between what was planned and what's actually happening on the ground, much earlier in the process.”

Comparing plans and reality through immersive monitoring

AIConstruct is developing an immersive platform that allows construction teams to compare a building's approved 3D model – often a building information model (BIM) file – with the actual state of the construction site over time.

Currently in the pilot phase, the platform is designed to be used once pre-construction planning has been completed and ground has been broken. Using a mixed-reality (MR) headset (currently Meta Quest 3), site teams perform periodic LiDAR-like scans of the construction environment to create snapshots of site reality at a given moment. The system then compares this scanned data with the original 3D building model to identify deviations. These may include misplaced structural elements or other discrepancies that could lead to rework – a big driver of cost overruns.

Rather than being a one-off diagnostic tool, AIConstruct is intended for ongoing monitoring: weekly or monthly scans allow teams to track progress and share visualised updates with colleagues who are not physically present on site. And while immersive visualisation has existed in the sector for some time, AIConstruct's novelty lies in the system's ability to compare live LiDAR-like scans with architect or engineer-approved models, enabling teams to detect divergences and respond accordingly – including via AI-supported guidance. Lelo describes this as creating a continuous, “bidirectional” feedback loop between plan and on-site reality.

Synchronising multiple technologies and layering assistive AI

AIConstruct's platform combines technologies including 3D building models, MR, LiDAR-like scanning, geospatial tools, and weather and traffic data. This involves extensive backend coding to synchronise the various technologies and datasets, as well as API integration to pull in the relevant external information (this helps to contextualise site productivity, for example, if a prolonged period of rainfall impacts work schedules). Lelo says: “We bring all of these technologies together with the single goal of finding out whether the plan matches the reality on the ground.”

AI is introduced primarily as an assistive decision-making layer. When deviations are detected, the system can generate recommendations based on available contextual data. One key development influenced by the Practitioners Hub sessions relates to global standards. After attending discussions on ISO standards and governance, the AIConstruct team integrated a rule-based feature allowing uploaded 3D models to be checked against ISO standards relevant to the built environment. Lelo notes that there are **over a thousand standards relevant to construction alone**, and therefore, despite the best efforts of architects, engineers and construction companies, violations are not always detected in the early stages of a project. This can be a prime driver of overruns and wastage.

Open-source foundations

AIConstruct is built to a large extent on open-source technology: Lelo explains that, as an early-stage startup, the company seeks to leverage community-built tools wherever possible. This includes components such as Cesium, which allows 3D models to be visualised geospatially. But while open-source tools provide flexibility and cost advantages, they don't always integrate seamlessly – for example, ensuring Cesium can accommodate IFC file formats (a standard format in architecture and engineering) requires additional coding – and sometimes performance issues can be exposed on construction sites that lack high-speed connectivity. In addition, large construction projects with big budgets typically use commercial software, so interoperability with AIConstruct's open-source elements becomes even more critical in order to lower the barrier to adoption.

“This means we have to be really good at understanding the open-source software,” says Lelo. “We may have to maintain our own version of a tool, or grow or adapt it in a way that suits our needs and context. The Practitioners Hub helped me understand the importance of documenting this process – what am I pulling in, and from where?”

Challenges and next steps: Earning sector trust and refining the technology

Introducing immersive AI into the construction sector means navigating a set of technical challenges (including the open-source and connectivity challenges mentioned earlier) and interpersonal dynamics. Construction is, in Lelo's words, a traditional, relationship-driven, male-dominated industry where new technologies – particularly those involving hardware such as MR headsets that can appear better suited to video games than construction sites – can initially be viewed with scepticism. Meanwhile, convincing teams to allow LiDAR-like scans of active construction sites and to share proprietary building models requires careful listening and transparency in addition to a compelling demo. Strong communication, humility and expectation management have become central to how Lelo and the AIConstruct team approach partnerships and pitching. "This isn't the sector for big egos or flashy products," says Lelo. "It's not the next billion-dollar dating app – you need patience and a real passion for the industry and for solving complex problems. It's definitely the hardest thing I've ever done."

In the short term, AIConstruct is focused on completing three pilot projects across different regions and documenting the outcomes in the form of publicly available case studies. For Lelo, these pilots are not only about technical validation, but about demonstrating practical value to potential construction partners. She is particularly interested in exploring the platform's potential in sustainability-focused contexts, including regions such as Scandinavia where environmental performance and compliance are closely monitored. The AIConstruct team is keen to hear from researchers with an interest in the topics of construction tracking and sustainability, or from prospective partners in the sector.

The next phase also involves working with pilot partners to define clear benchmarks for success and impact, as well as improving technical aspects of the platform such as the aforementioned interoperability with industry-standard commercial systems and formats – a key step on the path to wider adoption. Another area of planned development is expanding the standards-checking functionality to include regional as well as worldwide standards, while the team also has ambitions to incorporate digital twin technology that can automatically monitor factors such as humidity and light levels through the use of on-site sensors rather than manual sampling.

Looking further ahead, Lelo hopes to test the platform on larger infrastructure projects (for example, schools or hospitals) in which public accountability and procurement scrutiny are high. She concludes: “I want this to be an inclusive tool that construction teams who can’t afford the expensive systems can still use – but it has to be something they trust. We need to show that it works in real projects and that it helps people understand where time and money are really going. Ultimately, I’d like it to be a reliable reference tool that procurement teams or even lawyers can use when asking what went wrong and why. It’s the tool I wish I’d had when my own home was being built.”

Reflections on *The Turing Way* Practitioners Hub

“When you’re part of a community like the Practitioners Hub, you’re learning from real experts and from people who are actually using these technologies themselves. The sessions on data quality and readiness, for example, changed how I think about formats: I now appreciate the importance of factors like machine readability and proper versioning. Learning about ISO standards and how many there are in the built environment was a huge influence on our plans to incorporate this into our product. The whole programme has helped me approach this work more confidently – it’s the awareness and the trust in the knowledge coming from the community that makes a difference.”

Nompumelelo Mtsweni,
Founder of AIConstruct

Key takeaways

- Comparing planned building models with real-time site data can help reduce delays, cost overruns and unnecessary waste or corrective work in construction projects – all chronic problems in the sector.
- Integrating multiple technologies – rather than relying on a single breakthrough innovation – creates technical challenges but can produce practical product benefits and efficiencies. Similarly, open-source tools can enable cost-effective innovation but require careful integration and maintenance.
- Data readiness, version control and machine-readable formats are among the factors crucial to building responsible AI tools and generating reliable outputs.
- Rule-based AI can assist compliance checking by incorporating the 1,000+ global standards for the built environment sector.
- Trust-building, patience, humility and clear communication are important when introducing novel technologies into traditional, relationship-based industries such as construction.

Contributors and acknowledgements

This case study is published under *The Turing Way Practitioners Hub* 2025–26 Cohort – case study series. The Practitioners Hub is *The Turing Way* project that works with experts from partnering organisations to promote data science best practices. In 2025, The Turing Way team welcomed **Lelo Mtsweni**, **Guanhui Lee**, and **Mark Hester from AIConstruct** as Experts-in-Residence to discuss and share their implementation approaches to data science and AI, as well as build additional skills around best practices in responsible, ethical, and collaborative working. We thank them for leading the development of this case study.

The Turing Way Practitioner’s Hub was supported by Innovate UK BridgeAI from 2023–2026. BridgeAI empowers UK businesses in high-growth sectors, driving productivity and economic growth through the adoption of Artificial Intelligence. The programme bridges the gap between developers and end-users, fostering user-driven AI technologies.

With a focus on ethics, transparency, and data privacy, BridgeAI aims to build trust and confidence in the development of AI solutions. Strengthening AI leadership, supporting workforces, and promoting responsible innovation, BridgeAI shapes a collaborative and AI-enabled future.

BridgeAI is an Innovate UK funded programme, delivered by a consortium including Innovate UK, Digital Catapult, The Alan Turing Institute, STFC Hartree Centre and BSI.

The Practitioners Hub has also received funding and support from the Ecosystem Leadership Award under the EPSRC Grant EP/X03870X/1 & **The Alan Turing Institute**.

The Turing Way Practitioners Hub’s 2025–26 Cohort was co-delivered by **Arielle Bennett**, Senior Researcher – Open Source Practices and Dr Ann Borda, Senior Research Community Manager. **Stuart Gillespie** is the technical writer for this case study, and others in the series. **Léllé Demertzi** is the Research Project Manager and **Sofia Pires** is the Case Study Liaison for this case study.

The Turing Way Practitioners Hub, designed and launched in 2023 by Dr Malvika Sharan, aims to accelerate the adoption of best practices. Through a six-month cohort-based program, the Hub facilitates knowledge sharing, skill exchange, case study co-creation, and the adoption of open science practices. It also fosters a network of ‘Experts in Residence’ across partnering organisations.

For any comments, questions or collaboration with *The Turing Way*, please email: theturingway@gmail.com

Citation

Please cite this publication as:

Mtsweni, N., Gillespie, S., & Pires, S. (2026). AIConstruct: Tackling over-budget construction projects with AI-integrated immersive technology. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19116311>

References: <https://www.mckinsey.com/capabilities/operations/our-insights/dont-cancel-or-coddle-at-risk-capital-projects-challenge-them>
<https://www.iso.org/files/live/sites/isoorg/files/store/en/PUB100317.pdf>, <https://cesium.com/>

Innovate UK BridgeAI empowers UK businesses in high-growth sectors, driving productivity and economic growth through the adoption of Artificial Intelligence. We bridge the gap between developers and end-users, fostering user-driven AI technologies.

With a focus on ethics, transparency, and data privacy, we aim to build trust and confidence in the development of AI solutions. Strengthening AI leadership, supporting workforces, and promoting responsible innovation, BridgeAI shapes a collaborative and AI-enabled future.

BridgeAI is an Innovate UK funded programme, delivered by a consortium including Innovate UK, Digital Catapult, The Alan Turing Institute, STFC Hartree Centre and BSI.

Learn more at bridgeai.net

